

SUPPLEMENTAL RESULTS for NEUROLOGY/2020/170207

Impact of Cognitive Reserve on the Association of Vascular Brain Injury with Cognition: a Cross-Sectional Analysis of the PURE and CAHHM Studies

Supplemental Table 1. Characteristics of Participants with Complete Compared with Incomplete Information

Characteristics	Complete Data (n=10,027)	Missing Data (n=423)
Female	55.7%	54.6%
Age		
35-49	18.0%	20.6%
50-59	35.7%	39.5%
60-69	36.1%	29.6%
70-79	10.2%	10.4%
Age, years	58.2 (8.8)	57.4 (8.9)
Ethnic background		
East/SE Asian	10.6%	4.7%
White	83.8%	82.0%
South Asian	3.6%	11.1%
Black and Others	2.0%	2.1%
Highest Education Completed		
None	1.4%	4.8%
High school or less	17.2%	31.3%
Trade/Vocational	9.7%	13.1%
College/University	71.8%	50.8%
Married/Common Law	76.3%	73.4%
Participates in Social Groups	64.3%	53.3%
Moderate or Higher Leisure Time Physical Activity	55.5%	61.0%
Reported moderate or severe stress in past year	33.2%	34.7%
Height (cm): Females	162.3 (6.7)	161.1 (6.6)
Height (cm): Males	175.5 (7.1)	175.0 (7.1)
MRI Brain Measures		
Covert Brain Infarcts	5.2%	4.7%
Lacunar	3.7%	3.1%
Non-lacunar	1.5%	1.7%
≥3 CBI	0.6%	0.7%
High White Matter Hyperintensity (WMH)	5.9%	4.5%
MoCA ≥26	75.2%	58.6%
DSST Score	71.7 (16.8)	66.9 (16.4)

Supplemental Table 1 Legend: Values are percentages or mean (standard deviation). CBI, covert brain infarct; DSST, Digit Symbol Substitution test; MoCA, Montreal Cognitive Assessment.

Supplemental Table 2. Sensitivity Analysis including Lacunar Infarcts in the Definition of Vascular Brain Injury

2A. Predictors of MoCA	Without Interaction Between VBI & Cognitive Reserve Score		With Interaction Between VBI & Cognitive Reserve Score	
	Estimated Difference in MoCA (95% CI)	P-value	Estimated Difference in MoCA (95% CI)	P-value
Age (by 10 years)	-0.53 (-0.59, -0.48)	<.0001	-0.53 (-0.59, -0.48)	<.0001
Female	0.50 (0.41, 0.59)	<.0001	0.50 (0.41, 0.59)	<.0001
Vascular Brain Injury	-0.23 (-0.37, -0.08)	0.003	-0.21 (-0.36, -0.05)	0.009
Cognitive Reserve Composite Score (per additional point)	0.34 (0.31, 0.38)	<.0001	0.34 (0.31, 0.37)	<.0001
Interaction: VBI*Cognitive Reserve Composite			0.05 (-0.04, 0.13)	0.30

2B. Predictors of DSST	Without Interaction Between VBI & Cognitive Reserve Score		With Interaction Between VBI & Cognitive Reserve Score	
	Estimated Difference in DSST (95% CI)	P-value	Estimated Difference in DSST (95% CI)	P-value
Age (by 10 years)	-7.54 (-7.84, -7.24)	<.0001	-7.54 (-7.84, -7.24)	<.0001
Female	6.81 (6.30, 7.32)	<.0001	6.81 (6.30, 7.32)	<.0001
Vascular Brain Injury	-1.75 (-2.60, -0.90)	<.0001	-1.61 (-2.48, -0.73)	<.0001
Cognitive Reserve Composite Score (per additional point)	1.83 (1.65, 2.01)	<.0001	1.80 (1.61, 1.98)	<.0001
Interaction: VBI*Cognitive Reserve Composite			0.32 (-0.17, 0.80)	0.20

Supplemental Table 2 Legend: Vascular brain injury in this sensitivity analysis is defined as either any brain infarct (lacunar or non-lacunar) or high matter hyperintensity burden. Models are also adjusted for center (random intercepts) and ethnicity as a fixed effect. DSST, Digit Symbol Substitution test; MoCA, Montreal Cognitive Assessment.

Supplemental Table 3. Sensitivity Analysis Excluding Height from the Cognitive Reserve Composite Score

3A. Predictors of MoCA	Without Interaction Between VBI & Cognitive Reserve Score		With Interaction Between VBI & Cognitive Reserve Score	
	Estimated Difference in MoCA (95% CI)	P-value	Estimated Difference in MoCA (95% CI)	P-value
Age (by 10 years)	-0.56 (-0.61,-0.51)	<.0001	-0.56 (-0.61,-0.51)	<.0001
Female	0.50 (0.41,0.59)	<.0001	0.50 (0.41,0.59)	<.0001
Vascular Brain Injury	-0.36 (-0.54,-0.19)	<.0001	-0.32 (-0.52,-0.12)	0.002
Cognitive Reserve Composite Score (per additional point)	0.37 (0.34,0.41)	<.0001	0.37 (0.34,0.41)	<.0001
Interaction: VBI*Cognitive Reserve Composite			0.04 (-0.06,0.15)	0.42

3B. Predictors of DSST	Without Interaction Between VBI & Cognitive Reserve Score		With Interaction Between VBI & Cognitive Reserve Score	
	Estimated Difference in DSST (95% CI)	P-value	Estimated Difference in DSST (95% CI)	P-value
Age (by 10 years)	-7.71 (-8.01,-7.41)	<.0001	-7.71 (-8.01,-7.41)	<.0001
Female	6.80 (6.29,7.31)	<.0001	6.80 (6.29,7.31)	<.0001
Vascular Brain Injury	-2.23 (-3.23,-1.23)	<.0001	-2.03 (-3.18,-0.89)	<.0001
Cognitive Reserve Composite Score (per additional point)	1.95 (1.76,2.14)	<.0001	1.93 (1.73,2.13)	<.0001
Interaction: VBI*Cognitive Reserve Composite			0.21 (-0.40,0.82)	0.50

Supplemental Table 3 Legend: In this sensitivity analysis, the Cognitive Reserve Composite score consists of 1 point each for participation in social groups, being in a marital partnership, moderate or higher physical activity; and 0, 2, 2 or 4 points for less than high school, high school, trade school, or college/university education. Table 3 Legend: Models also adjusted for center (random intercepts) and ethnicity as a fixed effect. DSST, Digit Symbol Substitution test; MoCA, Montreal Cognitive Assessment.

Supplemental Table 4. Sensitivity Analysis Using Education as the Only Proxy for Cognitive Reserve

A. Predictors of MoCA	Without Interaction Between VBI & Cognitive Reserve Score		With Interaction Between VBI & Cognitive Reserve Score	
	Estimated Difference in MoCA (95% CI)	P-value	Estimated Difference in MoCA (95% CI)	P-value
Age (by 10 years)	-0.51 (-0.56, -0.45)	<.0001	-0.51 (-0.56, -0.45)	<.0001
Female	0.43 (0.34, 0.52)	<.0001	0.43 (0.34, 0.52)	<.0001
Vascular Brain Injury	-0.35 (-0.52, -0.19)	<.0001	-0.34 (-0.56, -0.13)	0.002
Cognitive Reserve Education Score (per additional point)	0.64 (0.59, 0.69)	<.0001	0.64 (0.59, 0.69)	<.0001
Interaction: VBI*Cognitive Reserve Education			0.01 (-0.13, 0.15)	0.89

B. Predictors of DSST	Without Interaction Between VBI & Cognitive Reserve Score		With Interaction Between VBI & Cognitive Reserve Score	
	Estimated Difference in DSST (95% CI)	P-value	Estimated Difference in DSST (95% CI)	P-value
Age (by 10 years)	-7.49 (-7.78, -7.19)	<.0001	-7.48 (-7.78, -7.19)	<.0001
Female	6.45 (5.94, 6.95)	<.0001	6.45 (5.94, 6.95)	<.0001
Vascular Brain Injury	-2.22 (-3.21, -1.23)	<.0001	-2.42 (-3.66, -1.18)	<0.001
Cognitive Reserve Education Score (per additional point)	2.76 (2.49, 3.04)	<.0001	2.79 (2.50, 3.07)	<.0001
Interaction: VBI*Cognitive Reserve Education			-0.24 (-1.11, 0.64)	0.60

Supplemental Table 4 Legend: The cognitive reserve education score is defined as 0, 2, 2 or 4 points for less than high school, high school, trade school, or college/university education. Models also adjusted for center (random intercepts) and ethnicity as a fixed effect. DSST, Digit Symbol Substitution test; MoCA, Montreal Cognitive Assessment.

Supplemental Table 5. Secondary Analyses of Vascular Brain Injury, Cognitive Reserve, and Montreal Cognitive Assessment Domains

Table B3	Odds (95%CI) of Deficits in MoCA Domains					
	Memory OR (95% CI)	Executive Function OR (95% CI)	Visuospatial OR (95% CI)	Language OR (95% CI)	Attention OR (95% CI)	Orientation OR (95% CI)
Age (by 10 years)	1.39 (1.32, 1.46)	1.19 (1.13, 1.25)	1.42 (1.34, 1.49)	1.23 (1.17, 1.29)	1.20 (1.14, 1.27)	1.20 (1.14, 1.27)
Female	0.51 (0.47, 0.56)	0.82 (0.75, 0.89)	1.08 (0.99, 1.18)	0.81 (0.74, 0.88)	1.15 (1.05, 1.26)	1.15 (1.05, 1.26)
Vascular Brain Injury	1.30 (1.07, 1.58)	1.19 (1.00, 1.41)	1.26 (1.06, 1.49)	1.22 (1.03, 1.44)	0.85 (0.70, 1.03)	0.85 (0.70, 1.03)
Cognitive Reserve Composite Score (per additional point)	0.90 (0.87, 0.93)	0.79 (0.76, 0.81)	0.84 (0.81, 0.87)	0.81 (0.78, 0.83)	0.84 (0.82, 0.87)	0.84 (0.82, 0.87)
Interaction: VBI*Cognitive Reserve Composite	1.01 (0.90, 1.12)	0.96 (0.87, 1.06)	1.05 (0.95, 1.15)	1.10 (1.00, 1.20)	0.98 (0.89, 1.08)	0.98 (0.89, 1.08)

Supplemental Table 5 Legend: Each column represents the findings from one multivariable logistic regression model, where the outcome is the odds of losing points (that is, impaired performance) in that domain. Table cell values are adjusted odds ratios (upper 95% confidence limit, lower 95% confidence limit). Odds ratios are statistically significant when the confidence limits do not cross 1.0. For example, the odds of memory impairment were higher in older persons and persons with vascular brain injury but were lower in females and persons with a higher cognitive reserve composite score, without evidence of interaction between vascular brain injury and the cognitive reserve composite score. Montreal Cognitive Assessment domains were defined based on Table 3 from Freitas et al (J International Neuropsych Society 2012;18:242-250). Models also adjusted for center as a random effect (with unstructured covariance matrix) and ethnicity as a fixed effect. OR, adjusted odds ratio.